

Optimized Speech Signal-based Diagnosis of Parkinson's Disease using Machine Learning Techniques – Augmented by An Efficient Feature Selection & Hyperparameter Tuning Approach

Deepak Painuli^{*1}, Suyash Bhardwaj², Utku Kose³

^{1,2}Gurukula Kangri Vishwavidyalaya, Haridwar, INDIA

³Suleyman Demirel University, Isparta, TURKEY

Email Id:- deepak.painuli@gmail.com ^{*1}, suyash.bhardwaj@gkv.ac.in², utkukose@sdu.edu.tr³

*Corresponding Author: - deepak.painuli@gmail.com

Abstract

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a neuropathological condition that deteriorates over the time, particularly in elder people. Symptoms of PD include difficulty in moving, autonomic dysfunction, depression, dementia, and visual hallucinations. Conventional diagnostic methods, could be subject to subjectivity as they rely on evaluation of motions that are frequently subtle to different eyes and hence difficult to describe, which could lead to misdiagnosis. While vocal abnormalities are connected to symptoms in almost 90% of PD patients at initial stages, as suggested by recent research on the diagnosis of PD. Higher efficiency & lower error rate of machine learning (ML) methods on complex & high dimensional data problems makes ML methods suitable choice for PD diagnosis task. This study presents implementation of 12 ML models i.e., Logistic Regression (LR), SVM (Linear/RBF), K-nearest Neighbor (KNN), Naive Bayes (NB), Decision-Tree (DT), Random Forest (RF), Extra Tree (ET), Gradient Boost (GbBoost), Extreme Gradient Boost (XgBoost), Adaptive Boost (AdaBoost) and Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP), to acquire efficient ML model, to accurately classify PD subjects using PD speech dataset. Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE) and Minimum Redundancy - Maximum Relevance (mRMR), feature selection (FS) methods were employed along with Grid Search cross-validation method of hyperparameter tuning during current study. Experimental results identified RF model with RFE generated feature subset (RFE-50) as best classifier among all 12 ML model withstanding improved accuracy of 96.46%, recall of 0.96, precision of 0.97, F1-score of 0.96 and AUC-score of 0.998, which observed to be highest among various ML models employed on same PD dataset in recent past.

KEYWORDS: Medical Diagnosis, Neuroscience, Parkinson's disease, Machine Learning, Data preprocessing, Feature selection, GridSearchCV.

1. INTRODUCTION

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a neuropathological condition that impairs human's ability to move. [1] It is observed that approximately 10+ millions of people world-wide are currently afflicted by PD, making it the second-most prevalent neurological condition after Alzheimer disease. [2-3] Regarding the prognostics, diagnosis, management, and treatment of the disease, the identification of PD positive people is essential. Parkinson disease is known to have a variety of early signs, including alterations in writing and speech. [4-5] Numerous research have demonstrated that this figure will increase in an ageing population because it is frequently observed in adults over 60. [6-7] PD typically defined by deterioration of some brain cell clusters, which are accountable for generating the neurotransmitters including dopamine, acetylcholine and serotonin. [8] Dopamine deficiency causes symptoms like anxiety, despair, weight loss, and vision issues. Poor balance, speech impairment, and tremor are some other signs of Parkinson's disease that can be found in patients. [10-12]

Observations from several recent studies suggest that 90% of person with PD experience speech and vocal issues, including monotone, dysphonia, and hypophonia. Consequently, the dilapidation of voice is perceived to be as the preliminary symptom of PD. [13-16] Although there is no known cause or treatment for Parkinson's disease, the availability of numerous medication therapy allows for significant symptom mitigation, particularly in the disease's early stages, which enhances patients' quality of life and lowers the pathology's projected cost. [17-19] One of the most notable clinical indications that can help confirm the diagnosis and gauge the severity of

Parkinson's disease is a change in the patient's voice. Voice measurement analysis is straightforward and noninvasive. Consequently, the measurement of speech may be utilized to monitor the development of PD. [20-21] To track the advancement of PD, a number of vocal-tests have been created, such as protracted phonations and flowing speech texts. Since voice signals are affordable and simple to use, monitoring and diagnosis systems have been widely adopted. [22-23] Conventional diagnostic methods, could be subject to subjectivity because they rely on evaluation of motions which are frequently subtle to different eyes and hence difficult to describe, which could lead to misdiagnosis. [24-25] Voice analysis-based studies might be categorized into four major aspect groups i.e., i.e., phonatory, articulatory, prosodic, and cognitive-linguistic. The majority of the time sustained vowels are used as the acoustic material for phonatory investigations, which are related to the glottal source and resonant structures of the vocal tract. [26, 27] Studies focused on articulatory aspects are more varied since there are more analytic options available. For example, the features or acoustic measurements analysed can be taken from various kinds of sound segments. It can be connected to articulator speed or acceleration, the type of segment transitions, or the evolution of formants, among other things. [28] The primary focus of prosodic studies is on paralinguistic elements such pitch fluctuation, syllable rate analysis, and emotional expression in speech signals. Finally, the cognitive-linguistic techniques examine the vocabulary, sentence complexity, phrase construction, and the presence of word repeats, among other manifestations, to analyze the abnormalities in cognitive behavior. [29, 30] This study falls under phonatory analysis, hence utilizes sustained vowels as acoustic materials due to the reason Sustained vowels are anticipated to produce straightforward acoustic traces that could result in consistent and, trustworthy evaluation of voice quality to some extent. Higher efficiency & lower error rate of ML methods on complex & high dimensional data problems makes ML methods suitable choice for PD diagnosis task. [31] As a result, this work makes an effort to first investigate a solely baseline traditional & simple ML-based models only and later fine tuned ML model for a PD early detection using the subject's voice samples.

This paper is structured as follows: the Section-2 provides support for the review of previous studies on PD identification using machine learning methods. The suggested methodology for PD detection is demonstrated in Section-3. The experimentation result's analysis and discussion are included in Section-4. Section-5 serves as the paper's final conclusion.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Various researchers previously made a number of significant attempts to diagnose Parkinson's disease using ML-based methods. The research that has been done previously to detect PD using speech samples as one of the subjects, are briefly reviewed and discussed in this section.

Achraf Benba et al. [32] suggested SVM-based classifier for detection of PD. Dataset utilized in this study includes 34 no of sustained vowels collected from 34 participants, 17 of whom had PD. 1 to 20 Mel-frequency cepstral coefficients (MFCC) were collected from each individual. SVM classifier along with LOSO crossvalidation (CV) is examined for different kernel values during classification process. Peak accuracy of 91.17% has been reported by SVM (Linear) using top 12 MFCC coefficients during model evaluation phase. Nissar, Iqra, et al. [33] proposed XgBoost-based ML model with RFE & mRMR - FS methods for detection of PD. Author also investigated performance of various ML models i.e., LR, KNN, SVM (Linear/RBF), NB, DT, RF, ET, and MLP along with proposed XgBoost model. Experiments result demonstrated that XgBoost model achieved highest accuracy of 95.39% among all utilized ML model.

Using weka tool Richa Mathur et al. [34] implemented and investigated ensemble learner of KNN & Adaboost.M1, Bagging and MLP-based model to detect PD cases. Experimentation results depicts superiority of ensemble learner (k-NN + Adaboost.M1) over Bagging and MLP model with an improved accuracy of 91.28% throughout classification phase of PD subjects. A. Yasar et al [35] proposed artificial neural networks (ANN) based model for the diagnosis of Parkinson's disease. One output feature and 45 selected features were used as inputs for the PD classification task. Proposed ANN-based model achieved 94.93% accuracy during classification phase of experimentation.

C.O. Sakar et al. [36] compared the various voice-signal processing techniques for PD identification. In this study, a novel function known as the tunable Q-factor wave-let transform (TQWT) was presented. TQWT fared better than cutting-edge speech signal-processing techniques, that were utilized to extract features for PD identification. Different classifiers were employed to several feature subsets, and estimates of ML classifiers were combined using ensemble methods. Apart from MFCCs and TQWT, mRMR feature selection (FS) method was

utilized during data preprocessing phase. Among all the considered classifiers, SVM (RBF) classifier shown highest accuracy of 86% for all feature-sets considered during model training and testing phase.

Pramanik, Moumita, et al. [18] presented NB-based ML approach for PD detection. This study utilized Fisher-score & mutual information (MI)-based FS methods along with hold-out CV to identify most important and non-redundant features from PD dataset utilized. Presented NB-based model demonstrated precision of 0.926 and accuracy of 78.97% during PD classification process. Barukab, Omar, et al. [2] investigated performance of different ensembles of decision tree-based models i.e., AdaBoost, RF & DT, along with information gain (IG) feature selection method on PD-voice dataset. Experiment results shown highest accuracy of 90.3% in terms of F1-score by AdaBoost method, making it suitable for imbalanced voice dataset of PD.

Joshi, Dhyey D., et al. [38] proposed stacking based ensemble learner for classification of PD using UCI-PD dataset. Classifier stack used in this study was formed using RF, SVM & KNN classifier along with ET and XgBoost model. study used Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) methods for dimensionality-reduction during experimentation process. Author also compared the performance of staking method with other ML models and results presented, shows improved efficiency of proposed model over rest utilized ML models withstanding accuracy of 91%.

Demir, Fatih, et al. [15] proposed L1-Norm SVM algorithms (CLS) and Chi-square FS-based approach to automate PD classification task. This study utilized three classifiers named KNN, SVM, DT and Bayesian algorithm for model development & optimization purpose. Experimentation results demonstrated superiority of KNN-based model over SVM & DT classifiers with an improved accuracy of 95.4%. Solana-Lavalle, et al [39] proposed a ML-based method along with wrapper-based FS method to automate PD classification task using PD speech dataset. Classifier employed during this study were KNN, MLP, SVM and RF. Result of study shows that SVM surpasses rest of classifier in terms of accuracy, while reducing feature space to 20 and withstanding accuracy of 94.7%.

Apart from above ML-based methods, many recent studies also utilize deep learning (DL)-based method for PD detection task using speech signals. Some of featured studies are as follows: -

Quan, Changqin, et al. [40] proposed a novel end-to-end DL-based model for PD detection from speech signals. This study utilized 2D-CNN & 1D-CNN methods to extract time series dynamic features and to capture the dependencies within these features. Performance evaluation shows promising accuracy of 81.6% & 92% on utilized database-1 (Chinese Language) and database-2 (Spanish Language) respectively. Study findings suggested that low-frequency region of the Mel-spectrogram found to be more dominant and significant than high-frequency region for PD detection from voice signal.

Yuan, Linlin, et al. [41] proposed a DL-based ensemble method to early diagnosis of PD using speech signal analysis. Proposed ensemble consists of DNN, LR & KNN classifiers and using ensemble voting method classification of PD subject is obtained. mRMR FS method was considered as feature selector throughout experimentation of this study and proposed method achieved improved accuracy - 95% and F1-score - 0.97 during PD detection task of this study.

Maskeliūnas, Rytis, et al. [20] demonstrated DL-driven voice analysis as promising tool for PD detection task. Study utilized ItalianPVS and Lithuanian voice dataset for development and evaluation of proposed DL-based model named U-Lossian. Proposed model achieved F1-score - 0.8974 & AUC - 0.9433 and F1-score 0.7778 & AUC - 0.8179, which found to be significantly improved than previously observed results mentioned in previous studies.

Khaskhoussy, Rania, et al. [42] proposed new DL-based approach to detect PD using speech signal. This study employs SVM & CNN as classification model along with Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM) as feature extractor. Using i-vectors extractor parameters, proposed DL-based method achieved perfect accuracy - 100% and F1-score - 0.98 over test dataset of 28 subjects.

Wang, Xingbo, et al. [43] proposed DL-based auxiliary diagnosis algorithm for PD diagnosis using sound signals. This study utilized ResNet50 as classifier as well as feature extractor and an improved Gbest Dimension Artificial Bee Colony (GDABC) algorithm as hyperparameter optimizer during whole experimentation phase. Proposed model was evaluated over Mobile Device Voice Recordings at King's College London (MDVR-CKL) dataset and clocked impressive accuracy of 96%.

Although DL-based methods demonstrated significantly improved & better performance during speech signal analysis-based diagnosis of PD in recent past, however limitation of DL-based methods i.e., large scale data requirement for reliable accuracy, higher complexity thus computationally intensive and overfitting issues

raised due to complexity etc. [44-48], mobilized this study to first search for efficient and simple ML-based methods for PD detection task and later optimize that ML model for best possible performance improved by optimized hyperparameter obtained through rigorous hyperparameter tuning using complete case evolution scenario based grid search method.

Various ML approaches have been used in recent research efforts done on speech-based PD detection, that can be seen from the review above. However, it should be noted that performance of all 12 state of art classifiers i.e., XgBoost, GbBoost & AdaBoost, were considered for model generation. Also, some studies made use of different feature selection (FS) methods and some not. Similarly, most of the studies doesn't imply the search of optimal hyperparameter for improved testing accuracy of considered ML-Model. Keeping above said in mind, this study investigated all the 12 ML-models, mentioned above, on PD speech dataset and also employs sophisticated FS methods like the mRMR & RFE, and Grid Search method for finding optimal hyperparameter of best three ML-Models i.e., RF, AdaBoost & MLP, for improved testing accuracy. Several performance criteria, including accuracy, recall, precision, F1-score, and AUC-score, were considered to assess efficiency of the suggested ML model. To determine the model's effectiveness, these results were also contrasted with those from a number of other ML models that were applied in the previously reviewed studies.

3. METHODOLOGY

Fig.1. Process flow of proposed method

Figure-1represents the major steps involved in methodology utilized during this study, which includes data collection, data preprocessing, data sampling, pre-evaluation or model development, feature selection phases, followed by post evaluation & model selection phase and at last PD classification phase. [49, 50] Standard scaling & normalization method is employed during data preprocessing phase, whereas oversampling method of data imbalance control has been used before data sampling step. Further pre-evaluation phase is followed by feature selection step, which includes selection of best 50, 10, 5 features using two well-known feature selection techniques RFE & mRMR. Next phase includes post evaluation of best three classifiers on selected feature subsets using default hyperparameter and tuned hyperparameter obtained via grid search optimization technique separately, to identify best classifier for final PD detection task. Once best classifier obtained through above experimentation, final stage was to employ it on test set of PD dataset. [51, 52]

3.1 PD DATASET

The gathering of data is the primary step in any classification process. Due to attribute/feature’s heterogeneity observed in different publicly available PD speech dataset, this study collected current PD speech dataset from UCI ML repository for experimentation purpose due to the reason this dataset owns separate dataset Training_Set for training (used during model development & evaluation phase of this study) & Testing_Set for testing (unseen to ML model till final testing) purpose for possible elimination of need of cross-database validation of ML model utilized in this study. PD speech dataset includes voice analysis data for both healthy and PD participants. As presented in figure-2, collected PD dataset includes 756 samples from 252 subjects (188 PD & 64 healthy). Total of 130 male and 122 female participants having age range of 33-87 years & 41-82 years respectively, contributed in above mentioned PD dataset. Following the doctor's examination, the sustained phonation of the vowel “/a/” was recorded from each subject 3 times with a microphone preset to 44.10 KHz as defined by protocol designed for recording patient’s acoustic [36, 53]. PD dataset contains total of 754 features corresponding 753 independent and 1 dependent features, which are categorized in Time Frequency Features, MFCCs, Vocal Fold Features, Wavelet Transform based Features and TWQT features groups. Brief information about independent features is presented in figure-2 above. [37]

Fig.2. Brief overview of PD Dataset

During data exploration class imbalance problem has been noticed and resolved via random oversampling method. As initially PD dataset consist of 564 observations of PD class (“1”) and 192 of healthy class (“0”) making it imbalanced dataset. Which may lead to biased performance by employed ML model as majority class (“1”) observed to be three times of minority class (“0”). To avoid this, minority class has been oversampled using random selection to equalize majority & minority class values (564 each), leading to balanced PD dataset. Glimpse of pre & post oversampling scenario are demonstrated in figure-3.

Fig.3. PD dataset's class balance - pre & post Oversampling

3.1.1 Brief Introduction on Oversampling

ML process flow utilizes different oversampling approaches to solve the issue of imbalanced datasets, when one class contains noticeably fewer samples than the other(s). These methods replicate or create synthetic samples in an effort to boost the representation of the minority class. There are various oversampling techniques to use i.e., Random Oversampling, Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique – SMOTE and Adaptive Synthetic Sampling – ADASYN. The ideal oversampling methodology varies on the particular problem and dataset, therefore it's always a good idea to try out a few alternative approaches before settling on one. To ensure an unbiased evaluation of the model's generalization capability and its efficacy in handling imbalanced data, keep in mind to employ the chosen oversampling strategy only on the training set and evaluate the performance of the applied ML model on the original imbalanced test set. To get the best outcomes, oversampling techniques should be used cautiously and in combination with other approaches including effective feature engineering, model selection, and hyperparameter tweaking. This study utilizes random oversampling techniques to control class imbalance present in the dataset, which randomly duplicates instances from the minority class until the number of instances in both classes is approximately equal. [55, 55]

3.2 Data Pre-processing

Data preprocessing in this study includes two processes named data Standardization and feature selection. Former one is typically a data preparation method required to squeeze feature's value scale to certain range to minimize computation of ML model when employed, whereas later one deals with dimensionality reduction process for making ML Model less complex by minimizing number of features to be considered for model training. [56-57]

3.2.1 Data Standardization

ML models works well and converge faster when features are roughly the same size and/or near to being normally distributed. This study makes use of Standard Scaler method for re-scaling feature values to unit variance and standard deviation as well, without compromising information present in feature. [55] Thus, leading to normally distributed features. Computation of standard scaler may be described as follows-

$$Z = \frac{(\chi - \mu)}{\sigma}$$

- where, μ = Training sample's mean.
- σ = Training sample's Standard deviation.
- χ = Training sample's value.
- Z = Standard score / z-scores of training sample

3.2.2 Feature Selection

As reason being PD dataset includes 754 features landing it be high dimensional dataset, which may lead to development of complex ML model and might demonstrate overfitting issue of ML model. To

avoid overfitting issue, only non-redundant and highly correlated features, that contributes most in target class prediction, needs to be included for model training purpose. Thus, post data standardization step, this study utilizes two well-known FS methods RFE & mRMR. RFE, wrapper-type FS method, using all independent features in the trainset as an initial point, try to obtain a features subset by reclusively removing features one by one until the predetermined number of features are left. [56, 58] Whereas mRMR, information theory-based FS method, ranks the features based on how relevant they are to the class label and how redundant they are with other features. Computation time consumption is higher in case of RFE, whereas mRMR observed to be less time consuming, thus mRMR is suitable option for high dimensional datasets, whereas RFE seems to be better choice low dimensional datasets. [59, 60]

After implementing RFE & mRMR feature selection method on PD dataset, this study identified three feature subsets of 50, 10 & 5 most relevant features out of total 754 features. Naming of RFE & mRMR generated feature subsets are RFE-50, RFE-10, RFE-5 and mRMR-50, mRMR-10 & mRMR-5 respectively. Brief description of individual feature subsets is as presented in table-1.

Table.1. List of selected features Subsets via RFE & mRMR FS method

	Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE)		Maximum Relevance - Minimum Redundancy (mRMR)
RFE-5	["mean_MFCC_2nd_coef"/"std_delta_delta_log_energy"/"std_6th_delta_delta"/"tqwt-energy-dec_26"/"tqwt_entropy_log_dec_12"]	mRMR-5	["std_9th_delta_delta"/"app_det_TKEO_mean_1_coef"/"tqwt_medianValue_dec_25"/"mean_MFCC_2nd_coef"/"tqwt_maxValue_dec_5"]
RFE-10	["mean_MFCC_2nd_coef"/"std-delta-log_energy"/"std_delta_delta_log_energy"/"std_6th_delta_delta"/"std_7th_delta_delta"/"tqwt_energydec_26"/"tqwt_entropy-shannon-dec_12"/"tqwt_entropy_log_dec_12"/"tqwt-entropy-logdec_33"/"tqwt-entropy-log_dec_35"]	mRMR-10	["std_9th_delta_delta"/"app_det_TKEO_mean_1_coef"/"tqwt_medianValue_dec_25"/"mean_MFCC_2nd_coef"/"tqwt_maxValue_dec_5"/"std_7th_delta_delta"/"std_8th_delta_delta"/"tqwt_entropy_log_dec_12"/"std_6th_delta_delta"/"tqwt_entropy_log_dec_26"]
RFE-50	["DFA"/"numPeriodsPulses"/"meanPeriodPulses"/"minIntensity"/"mean-MFCC_2nd_coef"/"mean-MFCC-5th_coef"/"mean_MFCC-6th_coef"/"std-MFCC_4th_coef"/"std_delta_log_energy"/"std_4th_delta"/"std_6th_delta"/"std_7th_delta"/"std_delta_delta_log_energy"/"std_4th_delta_delta"/"std_6th_delta_delta"/"std_7th_delta_delta"/"std_8th_delta_delta"/"std_9th-delta-delta"/"app-detTKEO-mean_9_coef"/"tqwt-energy-dec-25"/"tqwt-energydec-26"/"tqwt-energy-dec-27"/"tqwt-entropy-shannon-dec12"/"tqwt-entropy-shannon-dec-25"/"tqwt-entropy-log-dec-12"/"tqwt-entropy-log-dec-17"/"tqwt-entropy-log-dec-18"/"tqwt-entropy-log-dec-25"/"tqwt-entropy-log-dec-27"/"tqwt-entropy-log-dec-32"/"tqwt-entropy-log-dec-33"/"tqwt-entropy-log-dec-34"/"tqwt-entropy-log-dec35"/"tqwt-TKEO-mean-dec-12"/"tqwt-TKEO-mean-dec25"/"tqwt-TKEO-std-dec-11"/"tqwt-TKEO-std-dec-12"/"tqwt-TKEO-std-dec-13"/"tqwt-TKEO-std-dec19"/"tqwt_TKEO_std_dec_20"/"tqwt_medianValue_dec_36"/"tqwt_stdValue_dec_12"/"tqwt_stdValue_dec_33"/"tqwt_minValue_dec_17"/"tqwt_maxValue_dec_13"/"tqwt_maxValue_dec_17"/"tqwt_kurtosisValue_dec_17"/"tqwt_kurtosisValue_dec_18"/"tqwt_kurtosisValue_dec_36"]	mRMR-50	["std_9th_delta_delta"/"app-det-TKEO-mean-1coef"/"tqwt_medianValue_dec_25"/"mean-MFCC-2nd_coef"/"tqwt_maxValue_dec_5"/"std_7th_delta_delta"/"std_8th_delta_delta"/"tqwt_entropy_log_dec_12"/"std_6th_delta_delta"/"tqwt_entropy_log_dec_26"/"tqwt_kurtosisValue_dec_36"/"std_delta_delta_log_energy"/"tqwt_minValue_dec_12"/"DFA"/"std_8th_delta"/"std_10th_delta_delta"/"tqwt_maxValue_dec_12"/"std_11th_delta_delta"/"tqwt_maxValue_dec_11"/"std_6th_delta"/"tqwt_kurtosisValue_dec_27"/"std_9th_delta"/"tqwt_stdValue_dec_12"/"tqwt-kurtosisValue-dec-34"/"std_7th_delta"/"tqwt_stdValue_dec_11"/"mean_2nd_delta"/"tqwt_entropy_log_dec_27"/"tqwt_entropy_log_dec_11"/"std_10th_delta"/"locPetJitter"/"tqwt_minValue_dec_13"/"tqwt_entropy_shannon_dec_34"/"std_11th_delta"/"tqwt_entropy_log_dec_13"/"tqwt_entropy_dec_25"/"fl"/"tqwt_minValue_dec_11"/"std_4th_delta-delta"/"tqwt_kurtosisValue_dec_26"/"tqwt_entropy_log_dec_34"/"tqwt_maxValue_dec_13"/"std_delta_log_energy"/"numPeriodsPulses"/"std_4th_delta"/"tqwt_entropy_log_dec_16"/"std_12th_delta_delta"/"tqwt_stdValue_dec_6"/"tqwt_energy_dec_26"/"app_det_TKEO_mean_7_coef"]

3.2.3 Brief introduction to utilized feature selection methods

This section presents fundamental working concept of feature selection methods used in this study.

Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE)

RFE is a popular feature selection (FS) algorithm. Finding the subset of attributes that are most pertinent to a specific predictive modelling is its fundamental goal. RFE operates by repeatedly eliminating the dataset's least important features until the desired number of features is obtained. As a backward feature selection process, RFE starts with every feature and gradually eliminates them until the target numbers of features is obtained. The approach works well for high-dimensional datasets with plenty of features when it might not be viable to examine every feature subset. [61, 62]

Steps involved in RFE are as follows: -

1. Initially, all features present in dataset are marked relevant, and the preferred ML algorithm is trained on the complete set of features.

2. After that, the ML algorithm of choice is utilized to determine the feature importance ranking. Considering how each feature affects the overall performance of the model, its significance is assessed.
3. The dataset's feature with the lowest relevance score is removed, and the machine learning algorithm is then trained on the features that are left.
4. Repeat steps-2 & 3 till desired number of features are not obtained.
5. The model is next tested using the chosen subset of features on a different validation set.

□ **Minimum Redundancy Maximum Relevance (mRMR)**

mRMR is also a well-known FS algorithm that aims to recognize a feature subset from complete feature set, which consist of features that are both minimally redundant and highly informative. The algorithm evaluates redundancy and relevance of each feature and select a feature subset, including features that demonstrate symmetry between these two aspects. [47, 40]

Steps involved in mRMR are as follows: -

1. Initially, algorithm estimates the mutual information (MI), a measure of information provided by a feature about target feature, between each feature and target feature.
2. Next, algorithm assesses the redundancy between each feature pair by calculating their mutual information. Features are marked redundant if two features deliver comparable information.
3. Next, features bearing highest relevance are selected and included into the selected feature subset, where highest relevance refers to features having highest MI with target feature.
4. After that, the algorithm assesses the degree of redundancy between the selected feature and the other features. The average MI between the remaining features is subtracted after calculating the MI between the selected feature and each of the other features.
5. The algorithm chooses the feature and includes it into selected feature subset with the highest relevance minus redundancy score.
6. Repeat steps-4 & 5 till desired number of features are not obtained.

3.3 Model Training and Model Selection

During model training phase multiple ML models, as listed in classifier base mentioned in figure-1, were trained and evaluated on different feature subset, which were obtained from RFE & mRMR algorithm. Total of 12 ML classifiers i.e., LR, SVM (Linear & RBF), NB, KNN, RF, DT, ET, GbBoost, XgBoost, AdaBoost & MLP were utilized during model training process of pre-evaluation & model development phase of proposed methodology. Dramatical decrease in ML model' performance witnessed in previous studies due of leave-oneout subject validation CV [36, 63-65] leads current study to utilize most promising & well known 10-fold CV [66-68] for validation of ML models employed throughout this study, ensuring better control on overfitting issue of trained ML model. All 12 classifier were employed and evaluated on both unbalanced PD dataset (D1) and balanced PD dataset (D2) with their default parameter's values and sampling parameter "random state" preset to value 42 at this stage. On the basis of multiple performance metrics three best performer ML model i.e., RF, AdaBoost & MLP, has been identified for further stages of current study.

3.3.1 Brief introduction to adopted ML Classifier

□ **Random Forest (RF)**

Random Forest, a well-known ML classifier, is an ensemble learning type method which used to blend different decision trees in order to increase accuracy and decrease overfitting. To broaden the ensemble's diversity and decrease overfitting, the approach uses feature selection and bootstrapping with aggregation. [31, 41, 51]

Steps involved in Random Forest are as follows: -

1. At its first step, it performs data splitting to identify train set and test set out of data in hand. Former set is used to train the model, while later set is utilized for evaluation of model's performance.
2. By iteratively dividing the data into smaller subsets based on the most important feature, a decision tree is constructed using the training data at second step. The dataset is partitioned in a way that maximizes information gain or minimizes dataset impurity. For this process it uses bootstrapping, which is a technique that makes sure each tree is trained using a distinct subset of the data. The method randomly chooses a portion of the training data with replacement to generate numerous decision trees.
3. To find the best split, the algorithm chooses a random subset of features at each node of the decision tree. This procedure, known as feature selection, aids in lowering the correlation between the trees and boosting the ensemble's variety.
4. In next step, a random forest is created by combining several decision trees that have already been constructed. The result of each tree is counted as a vote in classification tasks, and the class with the most votes is predicted.
5. Lastly, the testing data are used to assess the model's performance. This stage assists in determining the model's correctness and if it is over- or under-fitting the data.

□ **Adaptive Boosting (AdaBoost)**

Adaboost is a ML algorithm that combines multiple weak classifiers to generate a strong classifier. Algorithm modifies the weights of the training set based on the misclassified samples or in other words gives higher priority to misclassified samples to increase probabilities of correct classification being done by classifier during next sampling. The final classifier will be a weighted blend of the weak classifiers. [42, 62, 69]

Steps involved in AdaBoost are as follows: -

1. Initially it Initialize weights for each considered sample by assigning equal weight to each of them.
2. Train any weak classifier, evaluate performance over predictions on train set and calculate weighted error rate (sum of weights - misclassified samples / sum of all weights).
3. Determine the weak classifier's importance, assuming that a weak classifier with a low error rate signifies higher importance.
4. Increase the weight of the misclassified samples, which highlights and leads to higher significance given to incorrectly classified samples in the forthcoming iteration.
5. Train a second weak classifier with the new weights. For the new weak classifier, repeat steps 3-4, and combine predictions of the weak classifiers according to the value of the predictions.
6. Use the combined classifier to make predictions on new data, and repeat steps 2 through 6 until the desired level of performance is attained, after a predetermined number of iterations.

□ **Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP)**

The MLP is a type of neural network that is widely used in machine learning and deep learning. It is a feedforward neural network that can address a variety of supervised learning issues. It works by initializing weights & biases, followed by propagating input forward through network while calculating error and backpropagating calculated error to adjust weights & biases, later updating the weights & biases till anticipated accuracy is not accomplished. [31, 62, 51]

Steps involved in working with MLP:

1. At very first step data preprocessing must be performed, which may include feature scaling, normalization, and removing any outliers or unnecessary features and train-test split.
2. In next step, Weights and biases must be initialized with random values after pre-processing data in hand. Each neuron's output is determined by its weight values, and the bias values aid in learning and decision-making for the network.
3. Next, the input is multiplied by the weight matrix and added to the bias vector in the forward propagation phase to produce the output of the first layer. In order to obtain the output of the following layer, the output is then passed via an activation function, and so on, until the ultimate output layer is achieved.
4. Next, the difference between the expected output and the actual output is calculated after the forward propagation phase. The weights and biases of the network are modified using the backpropagation algorithm to reduce error.
5. Using an optimization approach like gradient descent, the network's weights and biases are changed after the error has been calculated. To reduce the inaccuracy, the weights and biases are updated in the opposite direction as the gradient.
6. Repeat Steps 3-5 until the error is reduced or the desired accuracy is attained. The intricacy of the issue and the amount of the dataset determine how many iterations are necessary to achieve the target accuracy.
7. The trained MLP model can be applied to forecast new data with final weights & biases optimized in step-5.

3.4 Model Optimization

Post obtainment of best ML classifier through pre-evaluation step, next stage is to find optimal value of different model’s parameter’s value to achieve optimal prediction efficiency from employed model. Which is typically known as hyperparameter tuning or optimization process. A parameter configuration that is external to the ML model and whose value cannot be inferred from data is referred to as a model hyperparameter. These parameters describe crucial model characteristics including complexity and learning rate and frequently employed in procedures to assist with model parameter estimation. Searching of optimal value of model’s hyperparameter may be performed by manual search or by using tree-based algorithm i.e., grid search or random search. Manual search could be tedious task as one model might poses multiple hyperparameter with reasonably long value space. [70, 71] Therefore, ML practitioners generally make use of automatic hyperparameter searching algorithm like grid search or random search methods. Both methods train and evaluate model’s performance on different combination of hyperparameter values and returns the hyperparameter combination for with considered ML model demonstrate best classification performance. This study utilized grid search method of hyperparameter tuning as it searches parameters values in complete parameters combination space. Grid search method is evaluated for various hyperparameter’s values of three selected ML models i.e., RF, AdaBoost & MLP, which were obtained during pre-evaluation phase of current study. [72] Mapped hyperparameter search space and received optimal hyperparameters values using grid search method for above three models are enumerated in table-2.

Table.2. List of mapped hyperparameter search space and optimal hyperparameters values using Grid Search Method

Model Name	Hyperparameter Name	Hyperparameter Search Space	Optimal Hyperparameter Value
Random Forest (RF)	“max_depth”	[3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 15, 20, 30, 50]	15
	“n_estimators”	[10, 50, 100, 200, 300,500]	300
	“Criterion”	['entropy', 'gini']	entropy
Adaptive Boosting (AdaBoost)	“learning_rate”	[0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.5, 1]	1
	“n_estimators”	[10, 50, 100, 200, 300, 500]	300
	“Algorithm”	['SAMME', 'SAMME.R']	SAMME.R

Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP)	“hidden_layer_sizes”	[(10,), (20,), (30,), (50,), (100,), (200,), (300,), (500,)]	500
	“Activation”	['sigmoid', 'identity', 'tanh', 'relu']	relu
	“Solver”	['lbfgs', 'sgd', 'adam']	sgd
	“Alpha”	[0.0001, 0.05]	0.0001

3.4.1 Grid Search method

Grid Search is a popular hyperparameter optimization algorithm used for finding the best hyperparameters or set, for a ML model. Where hyperparameters are parameters, which are explicit to applied ML model and are not learned during training. Grid Search is a straightforward yet efficient technique for optimizing hyperparameters. However, it can be computationally expensive, particularly when working with a large dataset or a lot of hyperparameters.

For each hyperparameter, a grid of potential values is defined, and all conceivable combinations of the hyperparameters in the grid are then thoroughly searched. The algorithm trains a model on a portion of the data using each combination of hyperparameters, and then assesses the model's performance on a validation set. All potential grid hyperparameter combinations are put through this method many times. [31, 73]

The user can choose the performance metric that will be used to assess each set of hyperparameters, and it will depend on the specific issue at hand. For instance, the performance statistic for a binary classification task may be accuracy, precision, recall, or F1-score.

The method chooses the collection of hyperparameters that produced the highest performance on the validation set after all the models have been trained and evaluated. The performance of this final model may then be assessed using a different test set after using this set of hyperparameters to train it on the complete training set. [40, 74]

3.4.2 Brief Introduction of various hyperparameter □

max_depth

This hyperparameter describes the deepest individual decision tree that may be found in the forest. The number of nodes from a tree's root to its furthest leaf is referred to as the depth of the tree. You can restrict no of splits or layers in the decision tree by specifying the max_depth. Max_depth needs to be set to a precise value in order to manage the complexity and overfitting of each individual decision tree. Limiting the depth of the decision trees by using a lesser max_depth value produces simpler trees with fewer splits. While increasing the max_depth option permits the decision trees to grow deeper and produce more complicated models, this can assist minimize overfitting. [31]

□ **n_estimators**

The n_estimators hyperparameter defines number of decision trees to be considered in the forest. It regulates the random forest's "strength" or size. Up to a certain point, adding more estimators often improves performance by lowering the variance of the predictions and enhancing the model's overall resilience. While adding more estimators can improve the model's performance, doing so also increases processing requirements, extends training periods, and reduces overfitting. [41]

□ **Criterion**

The criterion hyperparameter determines function used to measure the quality of a split at each node of the decision trees in the forest. "Gini impurity", "entropy", and "log_loss" are often employed criteria. The Gini impurity, which quantifies the likelihood that a randomly chosen element in a dataset will be misclassified, favours splits that produce more homogeneous groups of data in order to reduce the likelihood of wrong classifications. In order to reduce the entropy in each node, splits that produce more homogeneous groups of data are chosen. Entropy is a measure of the average amount of information or uncertainty in a set of data. [51]

□ **learning_rate**

The `learning_rate` hyperparameter regulates how much each weak learner (base estimator) contributes to the ensemble prediction in the end. It serves as a scaling factor for each weak learner's predictions. It establishes the importance or weight that will be given to each weak learner's prediction when the ensemble is updated. Smaller values result in a slower learning process, which reduces the risk of overfitting and improves generalisation performance, whereas bigger values hasten the learning process, which may lead to a less robust mode and raise the chance of overfitting. [42]

□ **Algorithm**

The `algorithm` hyperparameter, which commonly takes the option of base estimators, such as decision trees, support vector machines (SVM), or other machine learning algorithms, specifies the base estimator algorithm used for training weak learners. The SAMME (Stagewise Additive Modelling Using a Multi-class Exponential loss) and SAMME.R (Stagewise Additive Modelling Using a Multiclass Exponential loss with Real-valued outputs) algorithms are used as the basic algorithm. In contrast to the latter, which is an improvement of the SAMME method that adds real-valued predictions from the weak learners, the former is particularly created for multi-class classification issues using a generalisation of the exponential loss function. It bases its final forecast on the probabilities that it has assigned to each class label based on the outputs of the weaker learners. [62]

□ **hidden_layer_sizes**

The number of nodes or neurons in each hidden layer of the network is indicated by the hyperparameter `hidden_layer_sizes`. The network may learn more complicated representations and recognise nuanced patterns in the data by using more neurons in the hidden layers. However, overfitting can result from having too many neurons. Given that it relies on the particular problem, the complexity of the data, and the availability of training examples, determining the proper size of the hidden layers can be difficult. It is standard procedure to start with a minimal number of neurons in the hidden layers and gradually increase or reduce their size depending on whether the model is underfitting or overfitting. [69]

□ **Activation**

The `activation` hyperparameter describes the kind of activation function applied to the neurons in the hidden layers and output layer of the network. The network can learn and express complicated correlations in the data thanks to the activation function's introduction of non-linearity. The model's capacity for learning, rate of convergence, and capability to handle various types of input are all impacted by the choice of activation function, making it a crucial choice. Although MLP offers a number of activation functions, the most used ones are "sigmoid," "tanh," "relu," and "softmax." [75]

□ **Solver**

The optimization procedure that updates the weights and biases during training is known as the `solver` hyperparameter. The MLP's effectiveness and rate of convergence are influenced by the solver selection. Three frequently used solver algorithms in MLP are limited-memory Broyden-FletcherGoldfarb-Shanno (L-BFGS), stochastic gradient descent (SGD), and adaptive moment estimation (Adam). The dataset size, model complexity, and computational resources all play a role in the solver selection process. Adam is frequently a suitable default option because it requires little hyperparameter adjustment and frequently delivers good performance. [76]

□ **Alpha**

The `alpha` hyperparameter in MLP often refers to the regularization parameter used to regulate how much regularization is performed to the neural network weights, preventing overfitting and enhancing the model's generalization capabilities. Usually, it is set to a very small positive number like 0.0001 or 0.001. The dataset and the specific task at hand determine the value of alpha. It has a connection to weight decay, commonly known as L2 regularization. Smaller weights are encouraged by an increase

in regularization caused by a higher alpha value. A smaller alpha value, on the other hand, lessens the regularization impact and enables the model to give the features bigger weights. [77]

3.5 Performance Metrics

Following the model optimization stage, ML model is put into practice, and results are generated as a class or a probability. The next stage is to use a test dataset and some appropriate performance metrics to assess the model's effectiveness during prediction of Parkinson disease. Various metrics, including accuracy, recall, F-1 score, precision, and AUC-ROC curve, were been employed in this work to evaluate the classification performance. It is crucial to pick the right metrics to assess the ML model since they have an impact on how performance is compared and monitored. [41, 73, 78] Brief introduction of these performance metrics is presented in next upcoming subsections.

3.5.1 Confusion Matrix (CM)

Confusion matrix (CM) is primarily a base performance metrics for evaluating a classification ML model. Almost every performance metric used for classification problem makes use of CM's parameters i.e., true-positive (TP), true-negative (TN), false-positive (FP) & false-negative (FN). As PD classification is a two class ("1" & "0") classification task, CM will be 2x2 matrix, where one dimension represents actual target value and second represents predicted value as demonstrated in figure-4. The basic terminologies of CM are as follows:

Fig.4. Confusion Matrix for binary classification problems

□ **True-Positive (TP)**

It can be described as the capacity of a model, to classify classes accurately as positive (+ve), such that if actual class is 1, the predicted class will also be 1. It is also referred as sensitivity as well as True Positive Rate (TPR) in percentage format and typically defined by equation-1.

$$TPR(sensitivity) = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

□ **True Negative (TN)**

It is described as the capacity of a model, to classify classes accurately as negative (-ve), i.e., if real class is 0, then the projected class will also be 0. It also known as specificity as well as True Negative Rate (TNR) in percentage format and generally defined by equation-2.

$$TNR(specificity) = \frac{TN}{TN + FP} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

□ **False Positive (FP)**

It represents misclassification of negative class to positive class label. In other words, the model predicts a class label of 1 while the initial class label was 0. It also known False Positive Rate (FPR) in percentage format and typically defined by equation-3.

$$FPR = \frac{FP}{FP + TN}$$

$$FPR = TN + FP \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

□ **False Negative (FN)**

It represents misclassification of positive class to negative class label. In other words, the model predicts a class label of 0 while the initial class label was 1. It also known False Negative Rate (FNR) in percentage format and generally defined by equation-4.

$$FNR = \frac{FN}{TP + FN} \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

3.5.2 Accuracy

It represents the proportion of correctly predicted examples to all the instances in the dataset. It is observed to be good performance metrics for classification only when there is a class balance in considered dataset. For imbalanced dataset it is not a recommended choice for performance evaluation of ML model. It is generally defined by equation-5.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

3.5.3 Precision

In terms of how many of the expected positive outcomes materialized, Precision measures how accurate your model is. It is determined by dividing the number of retrieved instances by the proportion of true positive relevant instances and typically defined by equation-6.

$$Precision(P) = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

3.5.4 Recall

It is also known as sensitivity and is described as the ratio of accurately predicted positive (+ve) classes to all positive occurrences. Whenever false-negative (FN) has a significant importance, recall should be model’s metric we utilize to identify our most promising model. It is typically defined by equation-7.

$$Recall(R) = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \dots\dots\dots (7)$$

3.5.5 F1-score

Circumstances, where one is unable to assess applicability of recall & precision metrics for one’s classification task, F1-score may be suitable choice for performance evaluation as it combines both recall and precision or in other context it stands for a harmonic mean of recall and precision. It is generally defined by equation-8.

$$F1 - Score = \frac{2 \times P \times R}{P + R} \dots\dots\dots (8)$$

3.5.6 AUC-ROC Curve

Area under the curve (AUC) - Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC) curve is a well-known probability curve between TPR & FPR, mostly used for classification models, where ROC is a probability curve and AUC is a measure of separability. This curve demonstrates how effective the classification model is at differentiating between classes. The ROC curve's y-axis displays the true positive rate, while the x-axis displays the false positive rate. AUC ranges in value from 0 to 1. The model performs extraordinarily well in terms of classification when the AUC is near to 1, but performs poorly in terms of separability and is unable to separate data when the AUC is close to 0.5.

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Experimentation process involved data exploration initially, during which class imbalance problem has been identified and resolved via random oversampling method. Initially PD dataset consist of 564 observations of PD class (“1”) and 192 of healthy class (“0”) making it imbalanced dataset. To avoid this scenario, minority class has been oversampled using random selection to equalize majority & minority class values (564 each), leading to balanced PD dataset.

After oversampling, this study pre-evaluated 12 ML models i.e., LR, KNN, SVM (Linear & RBF), NB, DT, RF, ET, GbBoost, XgBoost, AdaBoost & MLP, on both datasets D1 (Unbalanced PD dataset) and D2 (Balanced PD dataset) to observe performance enhancement of employed ML models. At this stage all models were employed with their default parameters only. Results of pre-evaluation are as presented in table-3 and figure-5.

Table.3. Pre-evaluation performance of different ML models

Dataset	D1		D2		D1		D2		D1		D2	
	ML Model Name		Accuracy		Precision		Recall		F1-Score		AUC	
Logistic Regression (LR)	0.837	0.8997	0.83	0.9	0.84	0.9	0.83	0.9	0.8601	0.9525		
K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN)	0.8722	0.9027	0.89	0.91	0.87	0.9	0.86	0.9	0.8911	0.9679		
Support Vector Machine (SVM-Linear)	0.8281	0.885	0.82	0.89	0.83	0.88	0.82	0.88	0.7633	0.8861		
Support Vector Machine (SVM-RBF)	0.837	0.9086	0.86	0.91	0.84	0.91	0.81	0.91	0.7019	0.9086		
Gaussian Naive Bayes (NB)	0.7621	0.764	0.78	0.77	0.76	0.76	0.77	0.76	0.773	0.7893		
Decision Tree (DT)	0.8149	0.9115	0.81	0.92	0.81	0.91	0.81	0.91	0.7233	0.899		
Random Forest (RF)	0.8502	0.9351	0.85	0.94	0.85	0.94	0.84	0.93	0.9292	0.9955		
Extra Tree (ET)	0.7797	0.8909	0.77	0.9	0.78	0.89	0.77	0.89	0.7435	0.9277		
Gradient Boost (GbBoost)	0.8238	0.9322	0.82	0.94	0.82	0.93	0.82	0.93	0.9151	0.9966		
Extreme Gradient Boost (XgBoost)	0.8546	0.9322	0.85	0.93	0.85	0.93	0.85	0.93	0.9254	0.9992		
Adaptive Boost (AdaBoost)	0.8458	0.941	0.84	0.94	0.85	0.94	0.84	0.94	0.8994	0.9869		
Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP)	0.859	0.938	0.85	0.94	0.86	0.94	0.85	0.94	0.8968	0.9838		

Figure-5 represents prediction performance of 12 ML models on both balanced (D2) and unbalanced (D1) datasets in terms of AUC-ROC (AUROC) curve. Higher the area under the curve lowers the misclassification rate of that ML model.

Fig.5. Pre-evaluation performance of different ML models using AUROC Curve

As demonstrated in table-3 and figure-5, performance increase has been observed in almost all ML model in terms of various performance-metrics, signifying the fact that ML models performs well when dataset provided, has predictor class balance. This ensures unbiased performance of applied ML model, by reducing misclassification count and upsurging of correct classification by ML model. As per above performance, this study considered D2 dataset for forthcoming experimentation process. Post pre-evaluation phase itself, this study identified top three ML model i.e., RF, AdaBoost & MLP, for further phases of current study.

Concurrent to pre-evaluation phase itself, feature selection (FS) phase has been implemented to identify three feature subsets including best 50, 10 & 5 features using RFE & mRMR FS method. Both RFE [RFE-50, RFE-10, RFE-5] & mRMR [mRMR-50, mRMR-10, mRMR-5] feature subsets have been investigated during this study to identify best FS approach using selected ML models on the basis of various performance metrics. List of feature subsets generated by both FS methods is presented in table-1 under section 3.2.2. Experimentation results on above mentioned subsets by RF, AdaBoost & MLP model with their default parameters, is presented in table-4 and figure-6 given below.

Table.4. Performance of RF, AdaBoost & MLP model (default parameters) models on RFE & mRMR feature subsets

ML Model Name	RFE	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	AUC	mRMR	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	AUC
Random Forest (RF)		0.9469	0.95	0.95	0.95	0.9979		0.9292	0.93	0.93	0.93	0.9933
Adaptive Boost (AdaBoost)	RFE-50	0.9498	0.95	0.95	0.95	0.9765	mRMR-50	0.9204	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.9414
Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP)		0.9734	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.99		0.9292	0.94	0.93	0.93	0.9813
Random Forest (RF)		0.9439	0.95	0.94	0.94	0.9922		0.9233	0.93	0.92	0.92	0.9867
Adaptive Boost (AdaBoost)	RFE-10	0.8702	0.89	0.87	0.87	0.9253	mRMR-10	0.8555	0.86	0.86	0.86	0.9062
Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP)		0.8851	0.89	0.88	0.88	0.946		0.8348	0.84	0.83	0.83	0.8928
Random Forest (RF)		0.8967	0.91	0.9	0.9	0.9785		0.9026	0.91	0.9	0.9	0.9793
Adaptive Boost (AdaBoost)	RFE-5	0.8259	0.83	0.83	0.83	0.8901	mRMR-5	0.8377	0.84	0.84	0.84	0.9017
Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP)		0.80823	0.81	0.81	0.81	0.8815		0.7876	0.79	0.79	0.79	0.859

Figure-6 represents prediction performance of RF, AdaBoost & MLP models on Both RFE [RFE-50, RFE10, RFE-5] & mRMR [mRMR-50, mRMR-10, mRMR-5] feature subsets in terms of AUC-ROC (AUROC) curve using model’s default parameters before model optimization.

Figure 6. Pre-evaluation performance of RF, AdaBoost & MLP (default parameters) models using AUROC Curve

Post pre-evaluation phase, next phase of this study was hyperparameter tuning. This phase was to further improve performance of selected ML (RF, AdaBoost & MLP) models by tuning their hyperparameters to optimal value. Grid search cross validation method (GridSearchCV ()) has been employed for model optimization or hyperparameter tuning purpose during current study. Different search space values of different considered models were supplied to grid search method and through rigorous processing optimal values of features were obtained. List of models-wise hyperparameter name, supplied search space values and received optimal hyperparameter values by grid search method is presented in table-2 under section 3.4.

After obtaining tuned hyperparameters of RF ['criterion': 'entropy', 'max_depth': 15, 'n_estimators': 300], AdaBoost ['algorithm': 'SAMME.R', 'learning_rate': 1, 'n_estimators': 300] & MLP ['activation': 'relu', 'alpha': 0.0001, 'hidden_layer_sizes': (500,),'learning_rate': 'invscaling', 'solver': 'sgd'] model using grid search, these models were evaluated on both RFE [RFE-50, RFE-10, RFE-5] & mRMR [mRMR-50, mRMR-10, mRMR-5] feature subsets using tuned hyperparameters for post evaluation in terms of accuracy, recall, F1-score, precision & AUC. Evaluation results of post evaluation of these model have been presented in table-5 and prediction performance of RF, AdaBoost & MLP models in terms of AUC-ROC (AUROC) is shown in figure-7.

Table-5. Performance of RF, AdaBoost & MLP model (tuned parameter) models on RFE & mRMR feature

ML Model Name	Feature Subsets	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	AUC	Feature Subsets	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	AUC		
subsets												
F1-Score												
Random Forest (RF)	Full Set	0.9646	0.97	0.96	0.96	0.9969	Full Set	0.9646	0.97	0.96	0.96	0.9969
Adaptive Boost (AdaBoost)		0.9557	0.96	0.96	0.96	0.9924		0.9557	0.96	0.96	0.96	0.9924
Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP)		0.9439	0.95	0.94	0.94	0.9905		0.9439	0.95	0.94	0.94	0.9905
Random Forest (RF)	RFE-50	0.9646	0.97	0.96	0.96	0.9981	mRMR-50	0.9438	0.95	0.95	0.95	0.9929
Adaptive Boost (AdaBoost)		0.9646	0.97	0.96	0.96	0.9889		0.9204	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.959
Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP)		0.9852	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.9965		0.9174	0.93	0.92	0.92	0.9714
0.9814												
Random Forest (RF)	RFE-10	0.9528	0.95	0.95	0.95	0.9923	mRMR-10	0.9204	0.93	0.92	0.92	0.927
Adaptive Boost (AdaBoost)		0.9027	0.92	0.9	0.9	0.9418		0.8997	0.92	0.9	0.9	0.9352
Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP)		0.9233	0.93	0.92	0.92	0.9658		0.9056	0.92	0.91	0.9	0.9145
Random Forest (RF) 0.9145												
0.92	RFE-5	0.91	0.91	0.9805	0.9203	0.93	mRMR-5	0.92	0.92	0.9776	0.88	0.88
Adaptive Boost (AdaBoost)												

Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP) 0.8791 0.89 0.88 0.88 0.9137 0.8908 0.9 0.89 0.89 0.9189

Fig.7. Post-evaluation performance of RF, AdaBoost & MLP (tuned parameter) models using AUROC Curve

Figure-7 represents prediction performance of RF, AdaBoost & MLP models on Both RFE [RFE-50, RFE10, RFE-5] & mRMR [mRMR-50, mRMR-10, mRMR-5] feature subsets in terms of AUC-ROC (AUROC) curve using model’s tuned parameters after model optimization.

Observations from table-4 shows dominance of random forest (RF) model in terms of prediction performance over rest two ML models when evaluation is performed on RFE & mRMR feature subsets using their default parameters. Except mRMR-50 subset, in all rest 5 feature subsets RF model demonstrated highest classification accuracy up to 94.39%, precision up to 0.95, Recall up to 0.94, F1-score up to 0.94 and AUC-score of 0.9922, while only in solo case of mRMR-50, MLP model shown accuracy of 97.37%. Also, it can be observed in table4 as well as in figure-6 & figure-8 that performance of all three models is significantly better in case of RFE

generated feature subsets rather than mRMR generated feature subsets demonstrating superiority of RFE feature subsets over mRMR feature subset for current study.

Further, on observing table-5, two important finding have been witnessed during post evaluation phase of the study. First observation witnessed shows dominance of tuned RF model over AdaBoost & MLP model with an improved accuracy of “96.46” %, precision of “0.97”, Recall of “0.96”, F1-score of “0.96” and AUC-score of “0.998” on every feature subset generated by RFE & mRMR feature selection methods including full set consisting of all features of PD dataset as well.

Fig.8. Performance comparison of RFE & mRMR feature subsets using default parameters

Second fact that may be noticed using table-5 and figure-7 & figure-9 that all three ML models (RF, AdaBoost & MLP) demonstrated significantly improved performance on RFE-50 & mRMR-50 feature subset of PD dataset even performance on full feature set also been employed. However, model’s performance on rest feature subsets i.e., RFE-10, RFE-5, mRMR-10 & mRMR-5 observed to be reduced to certain level. which signify better contribution of 50 features identified by RFE & mRMR FS methods on PD class prediction rather than 10 or 5 feature. It also represents that 10 & 5 feature may not be fair representative of complete PD dataset due to higher information loss received during feature selection. In contrast to 10 or 5 feature, 50 features subset shown enhanced performance of all three ML models even all feature of PD dataset were also been utilized. Which signifies higher information gain as well as correlation with target feature and also shows good candidature of identified 50 features against complete PD dataset without losing much information available previously in the dataset.

Fig.9. Performance comparison of RFE & mRMR feature subsets using tuned parameters

As demonstrated in table-3, RF, AdaBoost & MLP model were identified as most accurate model for PD detection task during pre-evaluation phase of this study. However, during post evaluation phase after model optimization, post evaluation result demonstrated significantly higher accuracy by RF-based model when employed with RFE feature subsets, even in almost every test scenario mentioned above on table-3,4 & 5. Although MLP-based model also demonstrated higher accuracy then RF-based model on RFE-50 feature subset,

but for the shake of model generalizability for almost every test scenario it can't be reported as best classifier for PD classification task.

On further evaluation when presented method, referred as random forest (RF) with recursive feature elimination (RFE)-(RF+RFE), is compared with past reported work on same PD dataset as presented in table-6, it is observed that diagnosis performance of RF+RFE model found to be significantly better than performance of employed models, reported in recent studies.

Table.6. Comparative Analysis of various models for PD detection.

ML Model	Proposed by	Accuracy (%)
Linear SVM	Achraf Benba et al. [32]	91.17
XGBoost	Nissar, Iqra, et al. [33]	95.39
kNN + Adaboost.M1	Richa Mathur et al. [34]	91.28
ANN	A. Yasar et al. [35]	94.93
SVM (RBF)	C.O. Sakar et al. [36]	86
NB+Fisher Score	Pramanik, Moumita, et al. [18]	78.97
AdaBoost + IG	Barukab, Omar, et al. [2]	90.3
Stack (RF+SVM+KNN)	Joshi, Dhyey D., et al. [38]	91
KNN+Chi Square	Demir, Fatih, et al. [15]	95.4
SVM + RFE	Solana-Lavalle, et al [39]	94.7
DL Model		
2D-CNN + 1D-CNN	Quan, Changqin, et al. [40]	92
DNN Ensemble	Yuan, Linlin, et al. [41]	95
U-Lossian Network	Maskeliūnas, Rytis, et al. [20]	94.33
CNN +SVM	Khaskhoussy, Rania, et al. [42]	98
ResNet50 + GDABC	Wang, Xingbo, et al. [43]	96
RF + RFE	Proposed by this study	96.46

As presented in table-6, RF+RFE model found to be reasonably best model among other ML-based model employed in recent past by previous researchers, on same PD dataset used in current study. The fact that the RF technique builds multiple decision trees and then aggregates the predictions generated by each decision tree was one of the fundamental factors in its success in creating an effective model for the problem. The regularization element of this technique, which substantially helped in decreasing the problem of overfitting, was another factor that contributed to its success.

5. CONCLUSION

Early diagnosis of Parkinson's disease (PD) is of utmost significance now a days in saving PD patients life beforehand. PD speech pattern analysis applications for developing predictive diagnosis and monitoring models have gained more attention and tremendous amount of progress has been witnessed in speech analysis methodologies recently by researchers. Since speech-measurements are non-invasive and speech-processing has long shown tremendous potential in the identification of PD. This research aims to evaluate the effectiveness of several ML-based classification methods. A speech PD dataset was used to apply the various classifiers, and several assessment criteria were compared using visualization and statistical analysis. In current study, the issue of PD diagnosis is handled using a ML technique, and multiple ML models have been utilized for its detection. By analyzing the vocal signals, this study primary goal is to demonstrate the PD diagnosis using various ML models using efficient feature selection (FS) methods (RFE & mRMR) and model optimization by grid search method. Experimentation finding suggested that random Forest (RF) model performs better in than any other

classifiers used in current study. The classification performance of RF model with RFE FS methodology was reported accuracy of 96.46%, precision of 0.97, F1-score of 0.96, Recall of 0.96 and AUC-score of 0.998, while, with mRMR FS technique it showed accuracy of 96.38%, precision of 0.95, Recall of 0.95, F1-score of 0.95 and AUC-score of 0.992. which is observed to be superior than all 12 ML methods investigated during this study. The performance of current method may be reliant on user's presumed deviations in dataset utilized, validation method considered, feature selection methods and hyperparameter strategy employed during experimentation. sample size of utilized dataset being used to train the model, is a limitation of this study, which seems to be affecting ML model's efficiency. Since the chosen dataset only contains 756 instances, a dataset with more samples would aid the model's ability to generalize PD diagnosis task. Apart from this, this study doesn't incorporate neurological conditions of the patients during PD classification might be another drawback and more studies may be done in neurological conditions of patients, apart from this, finding feature wise symmetric dataset and to develop & cross validates ML model using cross-database research further future scope of this study. Key finding suggested that, Random Forest (RF) method ought to be applied when creating a model for PD diagnosis task, recommends to use efficient feature selection techniques to lessen the complexity of the detection system for high dimensional dataset like PD speech dataset used in current study and suggested RFE method for feature selection tasks as it helped current study to achieve superior outcomes in current scenario. The suggested RF model's effective accuracy, precision, F1-score, recall, and AUC-score make it a trustworthy model for diagnosing Parkinson's disease.

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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in UCI Machine Learning Repository at <https://doi.org/10.24432/C5MS4X>, reference number [37].

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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